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Response from SciLifeLab and NBIS to the Swedish National Guidelines for Open Science

We, SciLifeLab and NBIS (*see Appendix*), are grateful for the opportunity to provide feedback to the National Library of Sweden on their draft for National Guidelines for Open Science. Much of what we do at SciLifeLab and NBIS embodies what the Guidelines are trying to achieve.

Below, please find our collaborative response to the Guidelines and we look forward to engaging with you, the National Library, further.

Areas within Open Science

The guidelines should be clearer on what specific licenses should be used for articles, data, software, protocols, and other research outputs. This clarity helps researchers avoid any confusion regarding what supports the goals of the guidelines. And licenses are essential to ensuring an efficient open science ecosystem, e.g., fostering reuse. A monitoring system aligned and integrated with the guidelines can track how licenses are being used and help with pinpointing areas where action and improvements are needed.

The guidelines maintain that 70 percent of (Swedish) scholarly articles were published open access in 2022 but this varies from the data that the COKI Project presents which is much lower. Likely it also varies between the common solutions used to assess these metrics (e.g., Web of Science, Europe PMC). It is essential that the guidelines push for open (citations) metadata and transparency in criteria and resources used between these services. Not only is this important at the national and international levels, but also at the organization, (project) team, and individual levels.

Coordination is needed at the national level to assist researchers with rights retention statements/addendums/waivers so that the process is streamlined. Institutional approaches are less efficient where a unified approach for publishers can be easier to work with. Compliance can be monitored and tracked at a national level.

Open Access books can be particularly challenging to fund according to local budgets which are more aligned with article processing charges or APCs. A landscape analysis of OA books costs should be conducted to determine how a nationally coordinated OA book funding pool can be leveraged to either subsidize the costs or fully pay for the costs. Alternatively, a national (or international) platform for publishing OA books can be supported with associated services to assist authors publishing on the platform.

FAIR is often used in the guidelines. Greater clarity on what it means, particularly what it will look like if the guidelines are followed, will be helpful. For instance, persistent identifiers such as DOIs are used for articles, ISSNs for books, so that the associated metadata is discoverable in global scholarly discovery systems. A section dedicated to describing and adding more context around FAIR in the guidelines would be helpful, seeing how it is used so often.

In addition to participating in and supporting international initiatives to reduce Open Access publishing costs, Sweden should also be engaged at the national level in Diamond Open Access initiatives, for instance, funded by Arcadia. In the meantime, supporting transparency of OA costs, particularly APCs in an open database would be helpful to establish reasonable/fair costs.

While privacy and sensitive data are addressed in the guidelines, for instance, that some data cannot be made openly available, there is no mention of the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, and how sensitivities working with communities and their data, can be addressed. A community forum and/or office can potentially assist with CARE related questions/approaches. A community forum at the national level is one place to start, to start discussions on the topic.

Ethical, legal and social issues regarding the use of data and bodily materials in health research is an area that is challenging for researchers and how to adhere to guidelines in relation to OA and FAIR. Not only are guidelines and recommendations sorely needed but assistance with associated questions is needed as well. It would be beneficial if the guidelines could aim at supporting Swedish research in this area in its goals, e.g. to establish a national ELSI Helpdesk such as the national ELSI Servicedesk in the Netherlands.

Data and the research outputs mentioned in the methods section should be treated equally and share similar goals. While sharing data is important, sharing other research outputs including software, protocols, educational materials and resources is equally important to supporting reproducibility of research. For instance, software is needed for understanding/analyzing/visualizing the data, they are interconnected. In addition, no mention of

open source software is made which has had a profound impact towards advancing science. The guidelines need to address research software related topics from software citation to the role of research software engineers.

Persistent identifiers, also mentioned in Support and Guidance, are a critical aspect to the FAIR principles mentioned throughout the guidance, and important to supporting quality metadata, exchange of information via interoperability, navigating access, and of course maintaining persistence. It is important to highlight the role of team science and the actors involved in curating resources and persistent identifiers (PID). The underlying PID infrastructure should be an open and free community resource.

FAIR can be applied to other outputs such as open science training material (e.g., as demonstrated through the work of ELIXIR and TeSS). Not only should the guidelines look at open science activities of researchers but also the work of other roles involved in team science such as training and how this work/material can be promoted leveraging the FAIR principles. This can also be expanded to other roles involved in connections with the public and building their trust, by capturing collaborative work with the community, aiding in the accessibility of research, and ensuring that broader impacts of research are discoverable. Note: Educational material, if shared openly and FAIR, not only further educates others but also builds an open science community of practice

We advocate for the sustainability/support for research infrastructure. Often the novel aspects of infrastructure are invested in versus simply maintenance. Community input and core metrics can be leveraged to support key investment but also there should be core principles that should be followed to further support open science. One example to look at here is how the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) is working to support essential open source software.

Players and their areas of responsibility, e.g. goal or motive

Researchers have a responsibility to be proactive and do open science, but it should be stressed that researchers must also be incentivised to do this by the academic reward systems. This responsibility includes helping to advance workflows and policies, but science involves teams, and more should be done to recognize and credit team science roles (e.g. data stewards, research software engineers, research infrastructure staff, etc, see CREDiT Taxonomy). A coordinated effort is needed to evolve promotion and tenure for researchers and other experts roles such as research infrastructure staff and data stewards (see Support and guidance response) but as part of those conversations, the roles and responsibilities of the teams should be recognized and rewarded to foster a more inclusive and fair research environment. Also, more responsibility should be shifted to research organizations that support and fund researchers. Researchers can only do so much vs the impact that policy and

supporting mechanisms can have towards shifting behaviors towards open science. For instance, grant applications, reviews, etc. should include measures to require open science elements.

A task force that coordinates national Open Science efforts between research funders, higher education institutions, and other stakeholders should prioritize and focus on what is achievable, given certain resources, and where the greatest impact can happen. For example, to achieve 100% open access for Swedish funded research, support and invest in services and workflows that make it easier to deposit, share, and make discoverable author manuscripts and require preprints (which facilitate more rapid feedback, collaboration, and open reviews). This is just one example though, similar prioritization should be done around data, code, etc.

International projects and services should be leveraged to implement a monitoring system (e.g., OpenAire Irish National Open Access Monitor) that is aligned and included with the guidelines. The monitoring system should include Open Science indicators (e.g., PLoS) and the guidelines should have a mechanism to incorporate information from the dashboard, to iterate and improve them. It is important for researchers to see that these activities will now be monitored, that they can check how they are doing against them, and have information on how they can improve. Researchers need to see that what they are doing has value, that it is having an impact, but also that they are being held accountable.

Not only is reproducibility a crisis in academic institutions, but also industry finds it challenging to trust the quality of research coming from these institutions. Open Science indicators have the potential of at least providing initial measures and filters for industry to be able to assess whether the research is robust and trustworthy. Industry is an important stakeholder to essentially test the effectiveness of whether research quality is improving per the guidelines and system.

Support and guidance

While development has gone into the infrastructure and services that support and advance the transition to open science, incentive structures such as promotion and tenure, and policies at research performing and funding organizations, have progressed very little. A national effort should be undertaken to convene stakeholders (e.g., universities, research organizations, research infrastructure) to align on policy and coordinate on the mechanisms to encourage and recognize open science activities (e.g., reporting, awards, outreach). There should also be coordination at the international level with groups such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). Additionally, key gaps in interdisciplinary and disciplinary infrastructure necessary to support open science incentive structures should be identified through these national efforts and the appropriate path to investment and support should be determined. One

area to note here are the international efforts around common vocabularies and crosswalks in metadata.

Researchers are already stretched on time. They need concrete guidance, i.e. instructions (see repository related commentary in General comments section), on how to do open science and yet material is numerous and not entirely clear on what they need to do. A landscape analysis of Swedish researchers is needed to understand current open science practices and trends. This analysis should be expanded beyond traditional metrics to include open science indicators (e.g. PLoS Open Science Indicators). The analysis can be used to develop clearer guidance and improved workflows for researchers, to ultimately improve open science activities and trends.

Data Management Plans (DMPs), Software Management Plans, and Project Management Plans are essential tools ensuring best practices in research management but their effectiveness is not realized due to their lack of machine actionability and flexibility in responding to projects that evolve. Sweden should tap into current national and international efforts to integrate machine actionable DMPs into research workflows and financially invest in these efforts for the benefit of the broader community. Persistent identifiers are invaluable to this effort, particularly identifiers that have been identified by our national PID strategy, and the Research Activity Identifier or RAiD, that will aid in curating/linking elements of the research process into something that is more valuable and impactful to the benefit of the research community and the public.

Open Science training should be mandatory as part of PhD programs, available to the greater science community for any upskilling needs, and should be coordinated at the national/international level, particularly regarding the essential elements of the curriculum. This should also be the case for team science roles (e.g., data steward, research software engineer) where Open Science training is required in order to fulfill these roles and also coordinated at the national/international level.

A national curriculum on BSc level for Data Stewardship is needed with additional domain specific MSc courses to meet the need and to support future researchers. Here, leveraging on recommendations from the EOSC-Association Task Force "Data Stewardship career and curricula" and other countries and organizations progress in this would be beneficial e.g., Dataversity training centre, DTL/ELIXIR-NL. Also, local efforts are underway to form a Swedish Data Stewards network, leveraging the work within RDA networks and there exists a European Data Stewards network coordinated by ELIXIR.

General or specific comments about the proposal as a whole or in parts, e.g. if something is missing

In addition to what was said above, more can be done in the guidelines to define/describe key terms. For instance, FAIR is mentioned earlier, but also accessibility, impact, methods, and other key terms can benefit from further description on what the guidelines are speaking to.

The guidelines are for new research, will it also apply to previously published research? Extracting value from previous publications (via text and data mining or TDM) can be invaluable but requires negotiating access with subscription databases and journals, even open sources. TDM can also be helpful for new research as many publications are still unstructured. Will the guidelines address TDM?

More can be done in the guidelines to explain to researchers and the community the advantages of open data. For instance, the motivation why open data can be beneficial not only in research but for the public. Examples would be helpful as well, what sharing data looks like and what it has led to.

Access to national health data in Sweden is a big stumbling block, particularly when it comes to safeguarding data. Data approaches such as de-identification, distributed computing, synthetic data, etc. are needed to make health data more open, but these approaches often involve technical solutions that need considerable development time. For example, leveraging foundational models in AI on large-scale health datasets is an increasingly important research space, and yet, authorization, interoperability, curation and other computational barriers are in the way. Efforts such as the NHLBI BioData Catalyst can serve as examples of how to invest in and foster collaboration around interoperability between the various stakeholders in the digital ecosystem while safeguarding data.

Researchers often face the challenge of where to share their data, whether in a local repository, institutional, or general. Coordination and facilitating collaborative efforts and resource sharing between repositories is needed. Investment in collaborative work between repositories, for example, like the NIH GREI initiative in the United States, can help with greater coordination between repositories. Ultimately, clearer guidance is needed on where it is best for researchers to share their data, particularly within their disciplines, and a national coordinated effort is welcome.

Scientists sometimes face a tension between open science and intellectual property (IP)/proprietary considerations. Guidance can be generic and unclear how to respond appropriately and researchers need assistance with navigating these questions. Leveraging the network of technology transfer offices and representatives at organizations and universities across Sweden as part of the national open science effort would be helpful in this case. Involving them in these efforts, particularly earlier in the research planning phases, and developing a support function for researchers is needed.

Appendix:

SciLifeLab, a national resource offering unique technologies and expertise to life scientists in fields like biomedicine, ecology, and evolution in Sweden, seamlessly integrates with our community of researchers, fostering collaborations across traditional boundaries with industry, healthcare, public research organizations, and international partners.

NBIS is the national bioinformatics infrastructure and SciLifeLab Bioinformatics Platform, also being the Swedish ELIXIR node. NBIS provides bioinformatics and data management support, infrastructure including tools and application expertise to high-performance computing, and training in advanced bioinformatics as well as research data management, FAIR training and Train-the-Trainer. One of our aims is to foster FAIR, reproducibility and Open Science as community practices.

SciLifeLab Data Centre is a central unit within SciLifeLab with the responsibility for IT- and data management issues, serving the SciLifeLab research and infrastructure, as well as the research programs for data-driven life sciences and pandemic laboratory preparedness. Data Centre provides services, and support, develops tools and databases, as well as facilitates the communication between SciLifeLab platforms, their users, and the research community. All our services and support strive for data to be handled according to Open Science and FAIR principles.

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